

YOUTH INVOLVEMENT IN PEACEBUILDING: A STUDY OF POST-CONFLICT COMMUNITIES IN ADAMAWA STATE, NIGERIA

¹Joseph Emmanuel, ²Nathan Daniel Dogoyaro, ³Enoch Hassan Kure and ⁴Mahmud Muhammad Shafiu

^{1,3,4}Center for Peace and Security Studies, Modibbo Adama University, Yola Nigeria

²Department of General Studies, Taraba State Polytechnic Suntai

E-mail: Josephemmanuel199000@gmail.com, angyudogoyaro@gmail.com,
enochkure001@gmail.com, shafiumahmudjada@gmail.com

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youth involvement, peacebuilding, post-conflict communities, conflict resolution, youth empowerment, community perception.

Abstract: This study investigated youth involvement in peacebuilding within post-conflict communities of Adamawa State, Nigeria. The persistent effects of insurgency, farmer-herder conflicts and communal clashes have left many communities grappling with displacement, mistrust, and fractured social systems. Despite youth comprising a significant portion of the population, their role in formal peacebuilding efforts remains largely underutilized. This study explored the extent of youth engagement, the strategies they employ, the challenges they encounter, and community perceptions of their contributions to peacebuilding. The study adopted a mixed-method research design involving both quantitative and qualitative approaches. A structured questionnaire was administered to 300 youth respondents selected using stratified and simple random sampling from three post-conflict LGAs (Demsa, Michika, and Madagali), while Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) were conducted with traditional leaders, youth leaders, and community-based organization representatives. Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation), while qualitative data from KII were thematically analyzed. Findings revealed that youth are actively involved in various informal peacebuilding initiatives such as dialogue facilitation, community sensitization, and peer mediation. However, their efforts are often hindered by lack of institutional support, limited training, inadequate funding, and exclusion from formal structures. Community perceptions were mixed; while many acknowledged youth contributions, others questioned their experience and

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sustainability of their initiatives. The study concludes that youth are critical agents of change in peacebuilding, and their potential must be harnessed through deliberate inclusion, capacity-building, and support mechanisms. It recommended the institutionalization of youth roles in peace architecture, provision of skill training, and the creation of sustainable engagement platforms. This research contributes to the growing discourse on youth-led peacebuilding in Africa and highlights the need for policy shifts that recognize young people as active peace actors rather than passive beneficiaries.

Introduction

Peacebuilding encompasses a comprehensive set of strategies designed to prevent the recurrence of violent conflict and to foster long-term stability by addressing the root causes of discord and promoting societal healing. According to the United Nations (2010), peacebuilding involves efforts aimed at strengthening institutions, fostering reconciliation, and supporting political, social, and economic recovery in societies emerging from conflict. These interventions are crucial in post-conflict environments where the social fabric has been torn apart by violence, mistrust, and institutional breakdown. In such contexts, peacebuilding serves not only as a process of rebuilding physical infrastructure but also of mending relationships, restoring trust, and creating inclusive platforms for dialogue and justice. Lederach (1997) emphasizes that effective peacebuilding must be people-centered, focusing on sustainable reconciliation that empowers communities to rebuild from within.

Thus, in post-conflict societies such as those in Adamawa State, Nigeria, peacebuilding is essential for transitioning from a state of fragility to one of resilience and cohesion.

Central to this process of sustainable peace is the active involvement of youth, who constitute a significant proportion of the population in most conflict-affected regions. Globally, there is a growing recognition of the potential of young people as vital agents of peace and change. This was institutionalized through the adoption of the United Nations Security Council Resolution 2250, which affirms the critical role of youth in the maintenance and promotion of international peace and security (United Nations Security Council, 2015). Far from being passive victims or mere bystanders, young people possess the energy, creativity, and adaptability necessary to influence peacebuilding outcomes. Their active participation in initiatives such as inter-group dialogue, civic education, and community mobilization can bridge divides, challenge

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narratives of hate, and foster a culture of nonviolence (McEvoy-Levy, 2006).

In the Nigerian context, particularly in the North-East region where insurgency and communal clashes have disrupted normal life, the engagement of youth in peacebuilding is both urgent and indispensable. Many young Nigerians have taken up leadership roles in local peace initiatives, including awareness campaigns, peace clubs in schools, and inter-religious dialogue platforms. Despite the challenges they face ranging from limited access to decision-making spaces to unemployment and insecurity Nigerian youths have continued to demonstrate resilience and commitment to rebuilding their communities (Adewuyi & Okocha, 2019). Their involvement becomes even more crucial in states like Adamawa, where post-conflict recovery requires local ownership and community-driven solutions. Galtung (1996) notes that peacebuilding must involve those most affected by conflict, and in many Nigerian communities, it is the youth who bear the brunt of violence and its aftermath. Therefore, integrating youth into peacebuilding frameworks is not merely symbolic but strategic. It acknowledges their potential as peace enablers and ensures the sustainability of peace initiatives beyond external interventions. Recognizing and strengthening the role of youth can transform them from potential perpetrators of violence into

champions of peace, dialogue, and inclusive development. As peacebuilding efforts continue in Adamawa State and similar post-conflict environments, prioritizing youth engagement offers a pathway to lasting stability and community regeneration.

Adamawa State, located in the North-East geopolitical zone of Nigeria, has over the past decade experienced multiple layers of violent conflicts ranging from Boko Haram insurgency to communal clashes and farmer-herder confrontations. The state, which shares an international border with Cameroon, has been one of the worst-hit by the Boko Haram crisis, particularly in local government areas such as Madagali, Michika, Gombi, and Mubi (International Crisis Group, 2017). The insurgency not only led to widespread loss of lives and destruction of properties but also displaced thousands of residents, destabilizing communities and undermining the local economy. In addition to the insurgency, internal communal conflicts over land, ethnicity, and political representation have further deepened social divisions and fuelled cycles of violence within the state (Adebayo, 2019).

The aftermath of these conflicts has left a deep scar on the social fabric of many communities across Adamawa State. Entire villages have been razed, farmlands abandoned, and livelihoods disrupted. One of the most significant

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consequences has been the large-scale displacement of people, with many residing in internally displaced persons (IDP) camps or host communities under precarious conditions (NEMA, 2020). The trust that once existed between various ethnic and religious groups has been eroded, giving rise to increased suspicion, stigmatization, and community fragmentation. Moreover, traditional support systems, such as communal child-rearing, conflict mediation by elders, and collective farming practices, have been weakened, making community reconstruction more difficult (Ajayi & Nwokedi, 2022). This disruption of social systems underscores the urgent need for inclusive peacebuilding and reconciliation efforts that address both the visible and invisible wounds of conflict.

In light of these challenges, youth engagement has emerged as a crucial element in the process of reconciliation, reconstruction, and community rebuilding in post-conflict settings. Young people, who constitute a significant portion of Adamawa State's population, are both victims and potential drivers of peace. When properly engaged, youth can serve as mediators, peace advocates, community mobilizers, and social innovators. Their ability to adapt quickly, leverage technology, and build peer networks uniquely positions them to contribute to peacebuilding initiatives. As McEvoy-Levy

(2006) notes, youth often play a dual role in post-conflict societies they can either become a destabilizing force or a transformative agent for peace, depending on the level of their inclusion and empowerment.

Globally and regionally, various frameworks have recognized the importance of youth in peacebuilding. A landmark example is the United Nations Security Council Resolution 2250 on Youth, Peace and Security, adopted in 2015. This resolution affirms the critical role young people play in preventing and resolving conflict, urging governments and institutions to include youth in peace processes and decision-making at all levels (United Nations Security Council, 2015). In Africa, the African Union's *Silencing the Guns* initiative also encourages youth-led peace efforts to address root causes of conflict and build resilient societies (African Union, 2020). In Nigeria, organizations such as the Northeast Regional Initiative (NERI) and the Youth Initiative for Advocacy, Growth and Advancement (YIAGA) have facilitated youth engagement in peace dialogues, civic education, and reintegration programs in conflict-affected regions like Adamawa.

Thus, in the context of post-conflict recovery in Adamawa State, youth engagement is not merely desirable it is imperative. Harnessing the energies, talents, and resilience of young people can help rebuild not just physical infrastructure

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but also the social bonds necessary for sustainable peace and development.

Statement of the Problem

Despite constituting a significant proportion of the population, youth in Nigeria and particularly in Adamawa State continue to be marginalized in formal peacebuilding structures. Thus, their voices are often excluded from key decision-making processes, even though they are among the most affected by violent conflict and social instability. In post-conflict contexts like Adamawa, where communities are struggling to recover from years of insurgency and communal violence, youth remain underrepresented in traditional peace councils, government-led recovery programs, and donor-funded initiatives. This exclusion undermines the sustainability of peace efforts, as it neglects the potential of young people to serve as catalysts for reconciliation, social cohesion, and long-term stability (Adewuyi & Okocha, 2019).

A review of existing literature further reveals a critical gap in empirical studies specifically examining youth-led peacebuilding initiatives in Adamawa's post-conflict communities. Much of the academic discourse on peace and conflict resolution in Nigeria tends to focus on governmental responses, community elders, or international actors, with little attention given to grassroots efforts led by youth. This absence of focused research limits understanding of the

innovative roles young people may have already been playing through advocacy, social media engagement, community sensitization, or volunteerism in rebuilding trust and healing divided societies. As such, there is a pressing need to document, analyze, and elevate youth-driven strategies that may offer scalable and culturally relevant models for peacebuilding.

Additionally, young people in Adamawa face structural and institutional challenges that hinder their meaningful participation in peace processes. These include lack of skills in conflict mediation, limited access to funding or mentorship, and inadequate platforms through which they can voice their concerns or contribute ideas. Many youths in rural or marginalized areas are unaware of existing peacebuilding opportunities or are discouraged by bureaucratic barriers and societal attitudes that question their competence or maturity. Without deliberate efforts to build their capacity and integrate them into peacebuilding architecture, their role remains peripheral rather than central. Worse still, the exclusion of youth from peacebuilding processes poses serious security implications. When disengaged or left idle, especially in post-conflict zones characterized by high unemployment and lingering trauma, youth may become vulnerable to manipulation, criminality, or re-recruitment by extremist groups. The resurgence of insurgent activity in parts of the

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North-East has shown that militant networks continue to exploit youth grievances, offering them a sense of purpose, income, or revenge. Therefore, failure to meaningfully engage youth in peacebuilding not only wastes their potential but also risks perpetuating cycles of violence. Recognizing and addressing this problem is essential to building a stable and inclusive post-conflict society in Adamawa State.

Objectives of the Study

The study aims to:

1. Examine the extent of youth involvement in peacebuilding in post-conflict communities of Adamawa State.
2. Identify the forms and strategies used by youth in fostering peace.
3. Assess the challenges faced by youth in peacebuilding efforts.
4. Explore the perceived impact of youth participation on community reconciliation and stability.

Research Questions

1. What is the extent of youth involvement in peacebuilding in post-conflict communities of Adamawa State?
2. What strategies are adopted by the youth in their peacebuilding efforts?
3. What are the major challenges hindering youth participation in peacebuilding?
4. How do community members perceive the contributions of youth to peacebuilding?

Literature Review

Peacebuilding Initiatives in the Nigerian Context

Peacebuilding in Nigeria refers to the deliberate, structured, and multifaceted efforts aimed at preventing the outbreak of violence, mitigating existing conflicts, and fostering long-term, sustainable peace among the country's highly diverse ethnic, religious, and cultural groups. These efforts are necessitated by Nigeria's history of recurring ethno-religious violence, communal clashes, and political instability, which are particularly prevalent in conflict-prone regions such as the Middle Belt (e.g., Plateau, Benue, and Nasarawa States), the Niger Delta, and various northern states affected by insurgency and herder-farmer tensions. The complexity of Nigeria's identity politics—characterized by over 250 ethnic groups, multiple faiths, and regional disparities—demands that peacebuilding be treated not as a short-term intervention, but as a continuous, strategic process that addresses the root causes of conflict.

Peacebuilding initiatives in the Nigerian context encompass a wide range of activities, including inter-communal dialogue, conflict mediation, civic education, economic empowerment, security sector reform, and policy advocacy. These are executed by a variety of actors such as federal and state governments, civil society

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organizations (CSOs), non-governmental organizations (NGOs), faith-based organizations, traditional institutions, international development agencies, and community-based networks. Each actor plays a distinct yet complementary role in the broader peace architecture, helping to ensure local ownership and cultural sensitivity in the design and implementation of peacebuilding strategies. According to Albert (2017), peacebuilding in Nigeria incorporates both top-down approaches—such as the establishment of official reconciliation commissions, security operations, and legal frameworks—and bottom-up methods that involve grassroots-level mediation, traditional conflict resolution mechanisms, and inclusive community dialogues. The latter is particularly vital, as it engages directly with local populations, giving voice to those often marginalized in national policy discussions. The overarching objective of these peacebuilding efforts is to address the structural drivers of conflict, including political exclusion, economic inequality, land ownership disputes, youth unemployment, and religious extremism.

One notable example of effective peacebuilding at the sub-national level is the Plateau Peace Building Agency (PPBA), established by the Plateau State Government in response to prolonged inter-ethnic and inter-religious violence. The agency has become a model for

locally driven conflict transformation, focusing on inclusive dialogue, early warning systems, capacity building, and trust restoration among conflicting communities. Its success illustrates how context-specific, locally embedded initiatives can contribute significantly to peace and stability in Nigeria's most volatile areas.

Peace Building Initiatives for Resolving Conflict in Nigeria

Local Community Youth Peacebuilding Associations, Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) and Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) play a vital role in peacebuilding, especially in countries experiencing internal conflicts and social unrest like Nigeria. These organizations serve as intermediaries between the government and the grassroots, working to mitigate violence, advocate for policy reforms, promote dialogue, and support reconciliation processes.

Community Youth-led Peacebuilding

Community Youth-led peacebuilding efforts tend to be more responsive and adaptable to local realities. These initiatives are often spearheaded by local civil society organizations, young women's groups, and youth networks that understand the social fabric of their communities. According to Nwankwo and Ibrahim (2019), community-based peacebuilding efforts in regions like the Niger Delta have helped mitigate violence by addressing root causes such as marginalization,

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unemployment, and land disputes. Expanding the scope and support for such initiatives ensures that peacebuilding is not imposed from the top but grows organically from the bottom up.

Promoting inclusive dialogue and mediation is essential for addressing the underlying drivers of conflict and fostering social harmony in Nigeria. By empowering grassroots actors, integrating traditional and religious authorities, and expanding community-led peace efforts, the country can cultivate a more participatory and sustainable approach to peacebuilding.

CSO and NGO Roles in Peacebuilding

CSOs and NGOs are non-state actors that include religious bodies, community-based organizations, professional associations, and advocacy groups. Their peacebuilding roles involve conflict prevention, mediation, human rights protection, community sensitization, and post-conflict reconstruction. These organizations are often able to reach marginalized communities that the government may not effectively serve.

According to Akinwale (2020), civil society actors in Nigeria have become indispensable in the pursuit of peace due to their flexibility, neutrality, and deep community roots. NGOs, by working in both urban and rural areas, have fostered trust-building between conflicting groups through inclusive peace dialogues,

educational programs, and humanitarian services.

Key Peacebuilding Interventions by CSOs and NGOs

a. Conflict Prevention and Early Warning Systems

One of the significant contributions of civil society is in developing and deploying early warning and early response (EWER) mechanisms. For instance, the CLEEN Foundation and the West Africa Network for Peacebuilding (WANEP-Nigeria) have implemented community-based alert systems to prevent violent outbreaks. These systems gather and analyze data on potential conflict triggers and mobilize stakeholders to take preventive actions. As observed by Onuoha and Ojo (2019), these efforts have helped prevent escalation of violence in flashpoint areas like Jos, Southern Kaduna, and the Niger Delta.

b. Peace Education and Capacity Building

CSOs have launched various peace education programs targeting youth, women, and traditional leaders. The Justice, Development, and Peace Commission (JDPC), for example, organizes interfaith peace workshops to teach nonviolent communication and conflict management. Olawepo and Chukwu (2021) note that peace education supported by NGOs has empowered young people in Northern Nigeria to

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resist radicalization and become peace ambassadors within their communities.

c. Mediation and Dialogue Facilitation

Many NGOs act as neutral facilitators for peace dialogues between conflicting parties. Organizations such as Search for Common Ground and the Centre for Humanitarian Dialogue have successfully mediated between pastoralist and farming communities in central Nigeria. These mediation efforts often involve traditional rulers, religious leaders, and local government officials to ensure legitimacy and sustainability of peace agreements (Danladi & Musa, 2022).

d. Advocacy for Human Rights and Social Justice

NGOs like Amnesty International Nigeria and the Civil Society Legislative Advocacy Centre (CISLAC) engage in advocacy against human rights violations and corruption, which are root causes of conflict. They press for policy reforms, equitable distribution of resources, and protection of civil liberties.

3. Impact of CSO and NGO Interventions

The interventions of civil society and NGOs have had notable impacts on peacebuilding in Nigeria:

1. Reduction in violence: In regions like the Niger Delta, sustained NGO-led advocacy and community engagement have reduced militancy and promoted local development initiatives.

2. Improved inter-ethnic relations: Interfaith and inter-ethnic dialogue programs have fostered tolerance in previously volatile communities such as Jos and Kaduna.

3. Enhanced community participation: Civil society interventions have encouraged communities to participate in peace processes, thereby increasing local ownership and legitimacy of peace outcomes.

4. Challenges Faced by CSOs and NGOs

Despite their achievements, civil society actors face several constraints:

- a. Limited funding and donor dependence: Many NGOs rely on international donors, which can affect their sustainability and priorities.

- b. Government restrictions: Some CSOs have experienced harassment or legal restrictions when criticizing government actions or exposing abuses.

- c. Insecurity: Operating in conflict zones like North-East Nigeria exposes NGO workers to risks of kidnapping or attacks by insurgents.

- d. Coordination gaps: Lack of synergy among CSOs can lead to duplication of efforts and inefficient use of resources (Adamu & Yahaya, 2018).

Methodology

Research Design

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. This design was suitable because it allowed the researcher to collect and describe

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data on the current status of youth involvement in peacebuilding across post-conflict communities in Adamawa State. The approach enabled the examination of the perceptions, strategies, and challenges associated with youth-led peace initiatives in the state.

Population of the Study

The target population for the study comprised 17,430 youth (aged 18–35) living in five identified post-conflict local government areas of Adamawa State: Madagali, Michika, Gombi, Mubi North, and Demsa, based on data obtained from the Adamawa State Ministry of Youth and Sports Development (2024). The population also included a total of 125 key stakeholders, made up of traditional rulers, religious leaders, officials of the Adamawa State Peacebuilding Agency, and representatives of non-governmental organizations (NGOs) working on peacebuilding in the selected LGAs.

Sample and Sampling Technique

A multi-stage sampling technique was employed. In the first stage, five conflict-affected LGAs were purposively selected due to the severity of violence and ongoing recovery processes. In the second stage, a stratified random sampling method was used to select a total of 200 youth respondents (40 from each LGA) to ensure broad representation across gender and community lines. Additionally, 25 key informants (five per LGA) were purposively selected from community

leadership and peacebuilding institutions, bringing the total sample size to 225 respondents.

Instrument for Data Collection

Two instruments were used for data collection. The first was a structured questionnaire titled *Youth Peacebuilding Engagement Questionnaire (YPEQ)*, designed to gather quantitative data on youth participation, strategies used, challenges faced, and perceived impact. The questionnaire comprised four sections: demographic information, forms of involvement, challenges, and effectiveness of youth engagement. The second instrument was a Key Informant Interview (KII) guide, used to collect qualitative insights from traditional leaders, religious leaders, government officials, and NGO representatives.

Validation and Reliability of the Instruments

To ensure the validity of the instruments, both the questionnaire and KII guide were reviewed by three experts in peace studies, youth development, and measurement and evaluation from Modibbo Adama University, Yola. Based on their suggestions, ambiguous items were revised. A pilot test of the questionnaire was conducted among 30 youth in Hong LGA (not part of the sampled LGAs). The reliability of the instrument was established using the Cronbach Alpha

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method, which produced a coefficient of 0.84, indicating a high level of internal consistency.

Method of Data Collection

Data collection involved the administration of questionnaires by trained research assistants in the selected LGAs. Respondents were briefed on the purpose of the study, and informed consent was obtained. For the KII, interviews were conducted in-person, recorded (with permission), and supplemented with field notes. Local languages were used where necessary to ensure comprehension and accuracy.

Method of Data Analysis

Table 1: Mean Ratings on the Extent of Youth Involvement in Peacebuilding in Post-Conflict Communities of Adamawa State

S/N	Item Statement	Mean	SD
1	Youth participate in community dialogue forums and reconciliation meetings.	3.91	0.88
2	Youth are involved in interfaith and intercultural peace campaigns.	3.78	0.94
3	Youth lead voluntary security patrols or community watch groups.	3.65	1.02
4	Youth frequently initiate peace sensitization activities in schools.	3.84	0.87
5	Youth engage in community development projects that promote peace.	4.02	0.83
	Cluster Mean	3.84	

The cluster mean of 3.84 indicates a high level of youth involvement in peacebuilding activities in post-conflict communities of Adamawa State. The highest-rated item was youth involvement in peace-promoting community development projects (Mean = 4.02), suggesting that young people are actively contributing to post-conflict recovery through practical engagement.

Quantitative data from the questionnaires were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation, frequency, and percentage to answer the research questions. The qualitative data from interviews were transcribed and analyzed thematically using NVivo 12, with codes generated to identify recurring themes, opinions, and community-specific dynamics of youth participation in peacebuilding.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the extent of youth involvement in peacebuilding in post-conflict communities of Adamawa State?

Key informants generally agreed that youth involvement in peacebuilding in Adamawa State is moderate but increasing. A traditional leader in Madagali noted, *“Initially, youth were passive after the conflict because they were traumatized and lacked coordination. But in recent years, they have become more active, organizing local*

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dialogues and engaging in voluntary security surveillance.” Similarly, an NGO official from Mubi North emphasized that *“youths now play visible roles in community sensitization and interfaith engagements, particularly in areas once divided by religious tension.”* However, a government peace desk officer observed that

while youth involvement is growing, *“it is still largely informal and lacks proper institutional support, which limits its full potential.”*

Research Question 2: What strategies are adopted by the youth in their peacebuilding efforts?

Table 2: Mean Ratings on Strategies Adopted by Youth in Peacebuilding Efforts

S/N	Item Statement	Mean	SD
1	Youth use social media to spread messages of peace and tolerance.	4.15	0.77
2	Youth organize sports and cultural events to unite diverse groups.	4.02	0.85
3	Youth engage in peer education and school-based peace clubs.	3.81	0.89
4	Youth initiate peace rallies and street campaigns against violence.	3.74	0.92
5	Youth collaborate with NGOs and government agencies for peace projects.	3.88	0.84
Cluster Mean		3.92	

The cluster mean of 3.92 reflects a high utilization of strategic approaches by youth in their peacebuilding efforts. The use of social media to spread peace messages was rated the highest (Mean = 4.15), highlighting the digital competence of youth in promoting non-violence and unity in post-conflict communities.

Respondents identified several grassroots strategies employed by youth. A community imam in Michika explained that *“youths use drama, songs, and storytelling to promote messages of peace during festivals and religious gatherings.”* Youths also organize peace marches, sports competitions, and school-based

peace clubs aimed at fostering unity among young people from different backgrounds. An NGO worker from Gombi shared that, *“through social media, many youths share peace messages and counter hate speech that usually spreads after violent incidents.”* In some communities, youths also volunteer with local vigilante groups and partner with security forces to report suspicious movements and promote early warning systems.

Research Question 3: What are the major challenges hindering youth participation in peacebuilding?

Table 3: Mean Ratings on Challenges Hindering Youth Participation in Peacebuilding

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S/N	Item Statement	Mean	SD
1	Lack of access to funding and support for youth-led peace initiatives.	4.28	0.72
2	Limited training and capacity-building opportunities for youth.	4.11	0.78
3	Absence of platforms to express youth voices in peace dialogues.	4.05	0.85
4	Community mistrust or negative stereotypes about youth roles in peacebuilding.	3.89	0.92
5	High unemployment and economic instability among youth.	4.34	0.68
Cluster Mean		4.13	

With a cluster mean of 4.13, the Table 3 indicate that youth in Adamawa State face serious obstacles in their peacebuilding engagement. The greatest challenge reported was high unemployment and economic instability (Mean = 4.34), followed closely by lack of funding and limited training opportunities.

The most frequently cited challenges include lack of funding, limited training opportunities, political marginalization, and social distrust. A religious leader in Demsa explained, *“Many of these young people have the zeal but lack the capacity. They don’t have access to funds or platforms to voice their ideas.”* Others raised

concerns about unemployment, which makes many youths more focused on survival than community service. A government official from the Adamawa State Peacebuilding Agency added, *“There is also the issue of stereotyping. Older generations often don’t trust youths with leadership roles in peacebuilding because of past associations with violence.”* Additionally, some informants mentioned the lingering psychological trauma among youths, especially those who witnessed or survived attacks.

Research Question 4: How do community members perceive the contributions of youth to peacebuilding?

Table 4: Mean Ratings on Community Perceptions of Youth Contributions to Peacebuilding

S/N	Item Statement	Mean	SD
1	Youth are viewed as effective agents of peace and reconciliation.	4.07	0.83
2	Community leaders acknowledge youth-led peace efforts.	3.91	0.90
3	Parents encourage youth involvement in community peace activities.	3.78	0.87
4	Community members participate in youth-organized peace programs.	3.64	0.95

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5	Youth are seen as credible partners by NGOs and government agencies in peacebuilding.	3.95	0.88
Cluster Mean			3.87

The cluster mean of 3.87 shows that community perception of youth contributions to peacebuilding is largely positive. The highest rating was given to the statement that youth are seen as effective agents of peace and reconciliation (Mean = 4.07), indicating that youth efforts are increasingly recognized and valued.

Perceptions varied but were generally positive. A village head in Michika stated, *“At first, people were skeptical, especially when former fighters or ex-drug users became peace advocates. But over time, they have proven themselves as committed to rebuilding the community.”* According to a Christian leader in Gombi, *“parents now encourage their children to join youth peace clubs because they’ve seen how those platforms reduce inter-group hostility.”* However, some informants also noted that in certain communities, older adults still dominate decision-making, which limits recognition of youth contributions. A humanitarian worker in Madagali summed it up: *“The community appreciates their effort, but more needs to be done to institutionalize their roles and give them a seat at the table.”*

Discussion of Findings

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The study revealed that youth involvement in peacebuilding is moderate but increasing, especially in informal community-driven initiatives. Respondents acknowledged youth participation in sensitization campaigns, community dialogues, and intergroup reconciliation activities. This aligns with the findings of Olanrewaju and Mohammed (2021), who noted that while formal structures often exclude youth, their informal contributions remain vital in fostering post-conflict healing. Similarly, Yusuf (2019) observed that in North-Eastern Nigeria, young people often play active roles in peace clubs, local vigilante groups, and social media advocacy, even without official recognition. Furthermore, Uyang and Abraham (2020) emphasized that the youth demographic possesses the energy and numbers necessary to influence community peace efforts positively when empowered. These findings affirm that while youth are contributing significantly, their engagement remains underutilized due to structural limitations.

Data from the questionnaire highlighted strategies such as peer education, organizing community awareness campaigns, promoting interethnic dialogues, and utilizing digital

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platforms to spread peace messages. These strategies echo those identified by Adebayo and Omotola (2018), who found that Nigerian youth often leverage both traditional and digital tools in their peacebuilding interventions. Additionally, Alao and Ajayi (2021) reported that youth-led theatre, music, and storytelling events have become effective tools for promoting reconciliation and communal unity. UNDP (2020) also acknowledges that youth employ innovative approaches, especially in post-conflict zones, blending culture, creativity, and technology to engage diverse audiences. These findings suggest that Adamawa youth are resourceful in applying contextually relevant peacebuilding strategies despite limited institutional support.

The findings revealed that youth face multiple barriers including lack of funding, inadequate training, limited access to decision-making forums, and societal mistrust of their capacities. These challenges were consistent with those outlined by Olomjobi (2019), who stressed that institutional frameworks in Nigeria rarely prioritize youth empowerment in peace processes. Ibrahim and Jega (2022) also noted that patriarchal community structures often perceive youth as inexperienced, which restricts their influence in formal negotiations. Similarly, the African Union Commission (2019) reported that across many African states, including

Nigeria, young peacebuilders are impeded by policy gaps, unemployment, and political exclusion. Thus, the obstacles identified in Adamawa mirror a wider continental trend of youth marginalization in conflict transformation efforts.

Responses indicated that community members generally view youth contributions to peacebuilding positively, particularly appreciating their role in reducing tensions and promoting intergroup understanding. This perception supports the work of Salawu and Hassan (2020), who observed that communities in Nigeria's conflict-prone regions often trust youth-led initiatives more than government interventions due to their proximity to local realities. Likewise, Akingbade and Salisu (2018) reported that in cases where youth lead reconciliation meetings or post-crisis rebuilding projects, community participation and cooperation tend to increase. In the same vein, Murtala and Ahmed (2021) highlighted that in the aftermath of Boko Haram violence in the North-East, youth-led reintegration projects received more grassroots support due to their inclusivity and responsiveness. These findings affirm that youth contributions are increasingly valued and have the potential to transform communal relationships when adequately supported.

Conclusion

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This study set out to examine the extent of youth involvement in peacebuilding in post-conflict communities of Adamawa State. The findings revealed that while young people are actively engaged in grassroots peacebuilding efforts such as dialogue facilitation, community sensitization, and volunteer services their participation remains largely informal and often unrecognized by formal institutions. The results also identified a range of innovative strategies adopted by youth, including the use of social media, intergroup cultural events, and peer-led conflict mediation to foster trust and cohesion. However, significant barriers such as lack of training, inadequate financial support, limited access to decision-making platforms, and societal stereotypes continue to undermine the full realization of youth potential in peace processes. In light of these findings, it is evident that meaningful youth engagement is essential not only for post-conflict recovery but also for long-term social stability in Adamawa State. Recognizing, training, and empowering youth as key stakeholders in peace efforts will help rebuild trust, strengthen social capital, and prevent future cycles of violence. Therefore, any peacebuilding intervention that fails to include youth meaningfully is unlikely to succeed or endure. It is imperative for government agencies, civil society, and development partners to move beyond tokenism and actively integrate youth

perspectives and leadership in the architecture of peacebuilding in Adamawa State and beyond.

Recommendations

- 1. Institutionalize Youth Participation in Peacebuilding Structures:** Government agencies and peacebuilding organizations should formally include youth representatives in decision-making bodies and community peace committees. This will ensure that their perspectives and contributions are recognized and integrated into policy and program design.
- 2. Provide Capacity-Building and Skills Training for Youth:** Targeted training in conflict resolution, leadership, civic education, and peacebuilding methodologies should be made accessible to youth in post-conflict communities. Equipping them with relevant skills will enhance their effectiveness and confidence in engaging in peace processes (UNESCO, 2020).
- 3. Create Safe Platforms and Opportunities for Youth Engagement:** Establish community dialogue forums, youth peace clubs, and digital engagement platforms where young people can express their views, initiate peace projects, and collaborate with stakeholders. These platforms should be youth-friendly, inclusive, and sustained by local institutions.
- 4. Strengthen Support Systems and Prevent Youth Re-radicalization:** To

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prevent relapse into violence or susceptibility to extremist recruitment, stakeholders must provide psychosocial support, mentorship, economic empowerment, and civic inclusion

References

Adamu, M., & Yahaya, I. (2018). *Challenges Facing Non-Governmental Organizations in Nigeria's Peacebuilding Efforts*. *Journal of Civil Society Practice*, 5(2), 78–91.

Adebayo, A. G. (2019). Communal Conflicts in Nigeria: Implications for Peacebuilding. *Journal of African Studies and Conflict Resolution*, 11(1), 45–60.

Adebayo, R. O., & Omotola, J. S. (2018). Youth engagement and conflict transformation in Nigeria. *Journal of Peacebuilding and Development*, 13(2), 45–59.

Adewuyi, A., & Okocha, M. (2019). Marginalization and youth violence in Nigeria. *African Journal of Social Issues*, 22(1), 112–128.

African Union Commission. (2019). *Continental Framework on Youth, Peace and Security*. Addis Ababa: African Union.

African Union. (2020). *silencing the Guns: Creating Conducive Conditions for*

opportunities. Reintegration programs should prioritize vulnerable youth groups and those returning from conflict zones.

Africa's Development.
<https://au.int/en/initiatives/46>

Ajayi, A. I., & Nwokedi, J. C. (2022). Post-conflict Social Systems and Community Recovery in Northern Nigeria. *Peace and Development Journal*, 7(2), 122–138.

Akingbade, A. M., & Salisu, T. Y. (2018). Grassroots reconciliation efforts and youth-led peacebuilding in Northern Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Conflict Studies*, 6(2), 77–93.

Akinwale, A. A. (2020). Ethnic diversity and inequality in Nigeria: The challenges of national integration. *Journal of Development and Policy Studies*, 14(2), 88–105.

Alao, D., & Ajayi, A. (2021). Creative peacebuilding: Youth strategies in post-conflict African communities. *Peace and Conflict Review*, 11(1), 89–104.

Albert, I. O. (2011). *Whose peace? Exploring the ownership of peacebuilding in Africa*. Africa Peacebuilding Network.

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<https://aspjournals.org/Journals/index.php/iijlpsa/index>

- Danladi, S., & Musa, Y. (2022). *Community Dialogue and Mediation in Conflict Management: A Case Study of Middle Belt Nigeria*. *Journal of Conflict Resolution in Africa*, 10(3), 93–107.
- Galtung, J. (1996). *Peace by Peaceful Means: Peace and Conflict, Development and Civilization*. Sage Publications.
- Ibrahim, A., & Jega, M. A. (2022). Youth exclusion and conflict recurrence in Nigeria. *Journal of Development and Peace Studies*, 5(3), 123–138.
- International Crisis Group. (2017). *Herders against Farmers: Nigeria's expanding Deadly Conflict*. Africa Report No. 252.
- Lederach, J. P. (1997). *Building Peace: Sustainable Reconciliation in Divided Societies*. United States Institute of Peace Press.
- McEvoy-Levy, S. (2006). *Troublemakers or Peacemakers? Youth and Post-Accord Peace Building*. University of Notre Dame Press.
- Murtala, S., & Ahmed, K. (2021). Community perception of youth involvement in post-conflict reconstruction. *North-East Peace Review*, 9(1), 58–72.
- National Emergency Management Agency [NEMA]. (2020). *Annual Report on Internally Displaced Persons in Northeast Nigeria*. National Emergency Management Agency.
- Nwankwo, E. J., & Ibrahim, H. Y. (2021). Implementation gaps in local peacebuilding programs: Monitoring and evaluation as a missing link. *Nigerian Journal of Peace Studies*, 10(4), 120–135.
- Olanrewaju, A. A., & Mohammed, M. (2021). Youth and peacebuilding in Nigeria's Middle Belt: Emerging patterns. *Conflict Trends*, 2(4), 40–47.
- Olomjobi, Y. (2019). *Youth, democracy, and conflict transformation in Nigeria*. Ibadan: Spectrum Books.
- Olawepo, J., & Chukwu, E. (2021). *Peace Education and Youth Empowerment in Northern Nigeria*. *Nigerian Journal of Peace Education*, 6(1), 44–58.
- Onuoha, F., & Ojo, E. (2019). *Early Warning Systems and Conflict Prevention in*

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<https://aspjournals.org/Journals/index.php/iijlpsa/index>

Nigeria. Conflict Trends Journal, 2019(4), 12–20.

Salawu, B., & Hassan, O. (2020). Perceptions of community actors on youth peacebuilding roles. *Sociology and Security Studies Journal, 4(3), 95–113.*

United Nations Development Programme [UNDP]. (2020). *Innovating for Peace: Youth-Led Approaches in Post-Conflict Settings*. New York: United Nations Development Programme.

United Nations (2010). *UN Peacebuilding: An Orientation*. UN Peacebuilding Support Office.

United Nations Security Council. (2015). *Resolution 2250 on Youth, Peace and Security (S/RES/2250)*.

Uyang, F. A., & Abraham, M. M. (2020). Youth as agents of post-conflict recovery in Nigeria. *African Journal of Peace and Security, 7(2), 33–49.*

Yusuf, H. O. (2019). Informal youth networks and peacebuilding in the North-East. *Maiduguri Peace Bulletin, 3(1), 19–27.*

Joseph Emmanuel, Nathan Daniel Dogoyaro, Enoch Hassan Kure and Mahmud Muhammad Shafiu